

ADVANCED MATERIALS, DIAGNOSTIC EQUIPMENT, AND QUALITY PROCESSING TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN INDUSTRY.

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Abstract: Modern industrial sectors rely on advanced materials, such as nanomaterials and smart composites, to enable new functionalities and improve product performance. Diagnostic equipment, including AI-driven systems and nanosensors, provides real-time quality control and process monitoring, ensuring precision and efficiency. Quality processing technologies, such as additive manufacturing and laser engineering, allow for the creation of complex geometries, reduced material waste, and customized products with enhanced durability.

Keywords: reduced material waste, nanosensors, nanomaterials, diagnostic equipment.

The authors identify the defects in additively manufactured machinery products made of stainless steel and various metallic alloys, such as cobalt, nickel, aluminum, and titanium alloys, which are earmarked for application in the aerospace industry. Mechanical machining, chemical etching, surface plastic deformation, ultrasonic cavitation abrasive finishing, laser ablation, and ion polishing in gas-discharge plasma are observed. The method of gas-discharge plasma processing for finishing laser additive manufactured parts and subsequent wear-resistant coating is proposed for the first time.

All the existing technologies are classified into three groups based on the possibility of volumetric processing and the nature of the exposure, which may be thermal, chemical, mechanical, or combined. The observed post-processing methods possess several disadvantages related to the nature of surface destruction, which influences the intensity of the wear on the working surfaces as a part of a unit or mechanism, along with the positive effect of plastic deformation and recrystallization of near-surface layers, erosion processes lead to stress states of the surfaces. Other words, magnetic flux density is used to create consolidated systems composed of many particles. One of the critical characteristics of these alloys is the Curie point—the temperature above which alloys lose their permanent magnetic properties, which determines their range of operating temperatures.

The magnetic properties also change depending on the alloy's phase (amorphous, crystalline), which is determined by powder production technology. Two main technologies are used to produce alloy powders: gas atomization and mechanical alloying. Both methods are implemented during powder metallurgy as the step before powder sintering and consolidation. Gas atomization allows us to obtain soft magnetic spherical particles of the mainly amorphous phase with a superior magnetic response, while mechanical alloying primarily produces smooth

particles that are more specific and irregular. In gas atomization, with a high dispersion of particle sizes and a particle size growth, the particle's phase can also be both amorphous and nanocrystalline.

Such powder production technology also prevents contamination of the cutting tools that happened during mechanical alloying. Mechanical alloying is mostly used to produce Fe-based nanocrystalline alloy powders. It should be noted that as the crystalline size increases, the alloy loses its soft behavior. The thermal stability of these alloys is also determined by crystalline growth, which depends on the apparent activation energy of crystallization. In this context, mechanical alloying is preferable for creating metastable alloys of nanocrystalline (supersaturated solid solutions or high-entropy alloys) and amorphous phases. The soft magnetic response can be improved by optimizing the milling modes in mechanical alloying and adding other elements. At the same time, B is responsible for reducing the crystalline size, which increases the magnetic response by decreasing the coercive force. In such alloys, B usually determines the formation of the amorphous phase or more refined nanocrystalline phase, often leading to a loss of saturation magnetization. Two-dimensional materials, particularly graphene, have recently become relevant in light of their specific carrier mobility in electronic device applications. Graphene layers are produced physically and chemically on a metal, semiconducting, and insulating material basis. The chemical-based growing methods are considered to be the most promising for providing high-quality graphene to meet the high demands of the market.

The most technologically promising graphene-growth method for a SiC substrate was achieved on Si- and C-faces. The type of face influences the properties of the graphene. The growth of the graphene on the Si-face leads to the formation of a C buffer underlayer between the graphene and Si-face. Charge transfer and substrate interaction of graphene grown on the Si-face affect its electronic properties compared to the C-face, which usually exhibits increased carrier mobility that depends on the layer's quantity. The most critical issue associated with graphene growth on the C-face is the thick layers and the inability to accurately monitor their number. Changes in the surrounding temperature can influence the properties of atomically thin graphene, making it more attractive for the sensory industry. A change in wetting properties is noted during surface functionalization, but the results of many studies on this topic are controversial. The primary sources of inconsistent graphene properties are surface charge, defects, and absorption of species (adsorbates). The adsorption of ambient molecular species on graphene surfaces leads to doping and changes in graphene's electrical and optical characteristics. However, when this process not properly controlled, it can lead to degradation, affecting the stability and reliability of the graphene-based device. The single-atom-thick graphene surface can absorb bulk aerosol and moisture contamination in the air. When exposed to moisture, graphene adsorbs contaminants on open surfaces at a temperature below the room's ambient temperature. It is important to keep such surfaces clear in order to maintain the properties of highly sensitive graphene. A change in the Raman spectrum of epitaxial graphene upon cooling due to moisture condensation can influence the evaluation of the material's quality. Raman spectroscopy is one of the most accurate research methods for detecting grown graphene contamination.

Heating these alloys can also influence the crystalline growth and reduce soft magnetic behavior. The thermal stability of the alloys was researched via thermal analysis of the apparent

activation energy of the crystalline growth and the Curie point. Exothermic processes occurred in the 450–650 K temperature range and were associated with tension relaxation.

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